

White Paper ID Number	W033
Title of White Paper	LRP2020: CASCA's EPO COMMITTEE WHITE PAPER: PROPOSED NATIONAL EPO PROJECTS FOR CASCA
ID of Associated Expression of Interest	E074
Topic Area of White Paper	outreach, education and teaching

Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

In this white paper, CASCA's EPO committee proposes a paradigm shift in the view of the Canadian Astronomical Society regarding its EPO efforts. Historically, because "EPO" is a very broad term, and because CASCA EPO is done primarily at the grass-roots level, and because CASCA EPO should touch a large variety Canadian demographics, it has been well nigh impossible for the CASCA Board to give consistent overarching meaningful direction to its EPO committees over the years, both ideologically and financially. For LRP2020, this EPO Committee proposes a way forward by focusing on National Projects.

Recommendation: The Canadian Astronomical Society fully support its current and future EPO committees in executing four NATIONAL EPO 'Pillar Projects':

- 1) Digital CASCA (e-CASCA)
- 2) Discover the Universe / À la découverte de l'univers (DU)
- 3) IAU initiated National Activities (N-IAU)
- 4) Westar Lectureship (CWL)

A full description of what comprises these 'living' National Pillar Projects, why they are needed, and a suggested plan for executing these projects to their maximum potential, including funding and coordination, is the purpose of this white paper.

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LRP2020: CASCA's EPO COMMITTEE WHITE PAPER:
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LRP2020 Committee Decision Criteria Questions

Because this white paper only pertains to EPO matters, the response to most of the Decision Criteria questions posed by the LRP2020 committee is "Not Applicable". The answers to the questions that do apply to this EPO white paper are:

4: *Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?* The relevant communities here are Canadians with a curiosity for astronomy and science, and the CASCA membership itself. This white paper shows both these communities support these EPO projects.

6: *In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favorable?* In the case of astronomy EPO, the benefits are more societal than economic – and thus difficult to quantify. But because the projects being put forth here are all National in scale, the societal benefits are large even if the funds injected are meager. Undoubtedly, as the funds injected grow the benefits will grow even faster.

8: *Does the proposed EPO initiative offer tangible benefits to Canadians?* If here we equate 'tangible benefits' with increases in scientific literacy, STEM advocacy, and fostering tomorrow's astronomers, then this EPO initiative will definitely benefit Canadians tangibly.

1. Background and Motivation

A recent inward-facing analysis of the ‘spirit of CASCA EPO’ was conducted using two broad tools: An anonymous two-question poll conducted at the most recent AGM in Montreal, and, a simple statistical review conducted to gauge the amount of EPO activity CASCA members organize and engage in, in a typical year. The details of these two ‘indicators’ are given in Appendix 1 and 2. So what does this tell us about CASCA EPO?

According to the first poll question, only 10% of responders indicated that they do not participate in EPO activities in a typical year. However, 50% participate in outreach between 1 and 4 times in a typical year, and 40% do so 5 times or more (110 responders is ~25% of the CASCA membership, so this sample size very likely reflects the opinion of the Society overall). So CASCA members believe that EPO is sufficiently important that they themselves instigate and engage in it.

This conclusion is heavily supported by the numerical data that CASCA members reported for 2018. ~550 CASCA members and their collaborators engaged, inspired, and educated, over 71,000 Canadians (the reporting form link is provided in Appendix 2). There was no ‘super attraction’ in 2018, like the solar eclipse of 2017 (where over 40,000 Canadians engaged with this one astronomical event), so this 2018 data reflects the usual day-to-day effort of CASCA members over a typical year.

And there are two important things to note regarding this survey: (1) It did NOT capture all of the year’s activity, as the reporting form is used on a voluntary basis (we estimate it is likely that the actual number of Canadians inspired was probably 30-50% higher than 71,000), and (2) this number does NOT include people reached through traditional media and social media venues. Some CASCA members reported reaching thousands via their digital efforts, but these numbers were not included in the tally of 71,000.

The second poll question was an attempt to gauge the overall sentiment of the CASCA membership about the importance of the EPO effort of their Society, relative to all of the various efforts and activities their Society advocates for. Very close to 50% of responders put EPO importance in the middle of the pack. The telling result is that outside of those 50%, twice as many responders put EPO importance in the high range than those that put EPO importance in the low range.

So what is the take-home message from this inward-facing analysis? It is not just speculation -> the majority of CASCA members do believe that astronomical Education and Outreach for the general Public is important, and volunteer their time for EPO activities, with amazing success.

There is another conclusion here, however. This EPO work is essentially all ‘grass-roots’ effort. Most EPO efforts done by CASCA members is not organized by CASCA’s EPO committee. In fact, one might argue that, if CASCA’s EPO committee did not exist at all, the state of CASCA EPO in Canada would still be very healthy. This begs the question; what is the purpose of CASCA’s EPO committee anyway?

2. CASCA EPO Committee’s National Mandate

The various committees within CASCA are member driven, and serve to connect professional astronomers to each other, and to all the various agencies and entities they require to effectively carry out their research interests. All these activities are therefore “inward facing”. But to be a well-rounded organization, Canada’s professional astronomers must make the effort to “face outward” and connect and engage with ordinary Canadians. Facilitating this connection must fundamentally be the driver of CASCA’s committee for Education and Public Outreach.

As a brief aside, we note that Canada has two other outstanding organizations for engaging the public in astronomy; the Royal Astronomical Society of Canada (RASC) and the Fédération des astronomes amateurs du Québec (FAAQ). What, if anything, distinguishes CASCA-EPO from RASC/FAAQ-EPO? This is an important question that is worth addressing because the simple answer is; EPO is EPO, regardless of the organization.

All astronomy EPO is important, but CASCA-EPO primarily connects a broad base of science experts to the public while RASC/FAAQ-EPO primarily connects astronomy enthusiasts to the public. While it is important for the public to engage with science advocates, it is more important that they engage with scientists. It is increasingly important that active researchers interact with the general public directly. Explaining complicated scientific concepts accurately, and at a level appropriate for their audience, is an important skill for all CASCA members. Engaging Canadians as professional researchers will build trust in the scientific community, increase scientific literacy and critical thinking, dispel misconceptions and misinformation, break stereotypes, and thus make the public better advocates for science. Whenever a CASCA member engages Canadians in EPO, they do this essential work.

These are some ideas that speak to the purpose of CASCA-EPO. As to the question of the purpose of CASCA's EPO committee, we need to look at the other fundamental aspect of our Society: CASCA is national in scope. Therefore, the outward facing activities that CASCA's EPO committee facilitates must also be national in scope. As noted above, education and public outreach activities, led by CASCA members does happen across Canada (and going forward CASCA's EPO committee will better encourage, support, and initiate this activity). However, this committee needs to fulfil its mandate by championing unique projects that are national in scope.

Seeking to define purpose for this committee, we present here four CASCA driven EPO projects we propose should become the 'Pillars' of National astronomical Education and Outreach for the general Public. In alphabetical order:

- [Digital CASCA \(e-CASCA\)](#)
- [Discover the Universe / À la découverte de l'univers \(DU\)](#)
- [IAU initiated National Activities \(N-IAU\)](#)
- [CASCA Westar Lectureship \(CWL\)](#)

Described in more detail below, each of these projects is fundamentally national in scope. Note that these projects are 'living projects', which all future CASCA EPO committees can continue to champion and grow.

Note also that none of these projects are completely new. Current and past CASCA EPO committees have dabbled to various degrees in some or all of these projects. *What we are proposing, however, is completely new*; that the Canadian Astronomical Society formally adopt these four projects as 'Pillars' of National Education and Public Outreach, and **fully support** its current and future EPO committees in executing these projects to their maximum potential.

3. The Four Pillars of National CASCA EPO

The following is a brief history of, and an overview of the goals of, each Pillar. Note that all Pillars facilitate an outward facing view of CASCA and its members to all the various demographics of the Canadian public across the whole nation – precisely the purpose of CASCA's EPO committee.

3.1 Digital CASCA (e-CASCA)

This broad Pillar incorporates all the web-based tools available now and in the future that CASCA could utilize to connect and engage with Canadians. The implementation of these tools would only be limited by CASCA's imagination.

The "key-stone" of e-CASCA is a bilingual website that Canadians prefer to go to for all their astronomical needs. A short list of attractors includes; scientific accuracy to counter fake news and misconceptions, learning resources for students, educational resources for teachers, promotion of CASCA's professional researchers and their discovery goals and the Canadian facilities they use, outreach training and resources for all CASCA members from graduate students to faculty, and much more. This key-stone website would also be the central host for the other three National Pillar Projects; N-IAU, CWL, and DU.

In addition to a key-stone website, e-CASCA would also employ social media tools to engage with Canadians. The two that are already in place are;

Facebook: @CASCA.Canada <https://www.facebook.com/CASCA.Canada/>

Twitter: AstroCanada-CASCA <https://twitter.com/AstroCanada>

Social media tools such as these are perfect for engaging Canadians in astronomical news and events inspired by Canadian researchers. Also, information related to the National Pillar EPO activities can be easily shared via this medium. e-CASCA is off to a humble start with CASCA's Facebook and Twitter presence, with usage and followers growing. Other tools are always being introduced, however (such as Instagram and Pinterest), which speaks to the need of staying current with web-based tools. One might even create the 'CASCA app'.

A recent (Sept. 2019) poll by 3M, showed that Canadians' trust in science is declining. While the overall opinion of science remains positive and most Canadians would encourage kids to pursue a career in science, the trend shows that people are becoming more skeptical of science and scientist. CASCA needs to get involved in this dialog and help address these issues by explaining how astronomical science is done, and the amazing research being done by Canadian astronomers. Science communication via e-CASCA will be central in this regard.

3.2 Discover the Universe / À la découverte de l'univers (DU)

As a legacy of IYA2009 in Canada, DU is a national and bilingual astronomical training program was founded and offered its first online workshop in 2011. The founding partners were CASCA, RASC and the FAAQ. Over the years, the program has grown and gained credibility and popularity with different audiences: K-12 teachers, science centres and museums, STEM outreach organizations and even international individuals and institutions. Teachers, in particular, are an important target group for Discover the Universe since astronomy is present in all provincial science curricula but many teachers feel uncomfortable teaching it.

Each year, Discover the Universe trains thousands of educators and helps them by providing content, accessible information and resources through online and onsite workshops. To increase CASCA's visibility and connection to Canada's science teachers, *DU has organized and hosted workshops for teachers at the CASCA annual general meetings since 2015*. This allows teachers in a different city every year to receive training and information on the latest scientific discoveries. These workshops are very successful, and the goal is to continue offering them in the years to come.

Discover the Universe, now offered primarily by the Dunlap Institute at the University of Toronto in collaboration with CASCA and the Centre for Research in Astrophysics in Québec - CRAQ, is now stronger than ever and has many ongoing projects and partnerships. The goal for the coming years is to grow the program by offering more workshops, developing new resources and reaching more educators across Canada. Beyond providing these resources to teachers, DU plans to expand these offers to graduate students, and CASCA members in general, to further serve CASCA EPO's mandate to engage the public as a scientific community.

Arguably, DU is the most successful and popular national Astronomy EPO program in Canada today. Often the acronym 'EPO' is shortened to 'outreach' because the importance of education is overlooked. This is why this Pillar is particularly important *because its focus is education*; education for science educators, education for CASCA members, and education for the general public. This National Pillar puts the 'E' back in 'EPO'.

3.3 IAU initiated National Activities (N-IAU)

Although an official reference wasn't found, we have heard it said that 'CASCA existed originally to support the activities of the International Astronomical Union in Canada', including EPO. So, although the invitation to collaborate goes far back in time, very few IAU inspired National EPO activities have been championed in Canada (since IYA2009). This year, however, CASCA is participating in the IAU's ExoWorld Naming Contest created as part of the IAU centenary celebrations.

This has been a very positive experience for several reasons. On the national level the next generation of astronomers are getting inspired about space. And not only are science teachers, their students, and the Canadian public engaging in astronomy, they are also learning about an organization called CASCA. Additionally, the EPO Committee has gained valuable experience in coordinating a nationally focussed activity which involved; social media as the primary communication tool, coordinating with the IAU EPO office, and the formation of a panel of judges from across the country. One essential lesson learned is that national level outreach events require a strong social media presence.

The deadline for submissions from the public has passed, so the vetting and judging phase has begun. The ExoWorld Naming contest will conclude later this year. Because many other countries are also involved, this N-IAU activity is truly international. Getting involved in IAU initiated activities will help put CASCA EPO on the international stage, potentially opening the door to important collaborations and projects in future.

Having gained valuable experience with this IAU initiated event, and realizing that this type of engagement fills a huge void in CASCA <-> public interaction, we advocate that N-IAU activities should take place annually as a Pillar of CASCA EPO.

3.4 CASCA Westar Lectureship (CWL)

In 2000, an agreement between CASCA and Westar – a consortium of universities in Western Canada, including the universities of British Columbia, Victoria, Notre Dame (in Nelson), Calgary, Alberta, and Lethbridge – entrusted a part of the funds remaining after the cancellation of the QEII telescope to a public education and outreach program, which would contribute to the advancement of astronomy in Canada. This program was to include (but was not limited to) the creation of a national lectureship, which is now called the CASCA-Westar Lectureship (CWL).

The most recent efforts to restart the CWL began in 2016 through the CASCA EPO committee. The CWL makes it possible for astronomers to share the excitement of the most recent discoveries in astronomy with school students and the general public. The primary objective of the CWL is to provide outreach to under-served (often remote) communities such as those without access to nearby post-secondary institutions with astronomy programs and facilities.

Outreach efforts, while they may be national or internationally focused, should also make an effort to engage with the host communities of the sponsoring institution or facility, respecting local languages, sky knowledge and the desires of that community – something this EPO Committee has learned is especially important when visiting Indigenous communities (e.g., “two-eyed seeing”, a term coined by Mi'kmaq Elder Albert Marshall; see this link for more details <https://www.edcan.ca/articles/the-best-of-both-worlds/>).

CWL visits are awarded on a competitive basis and applications are solicited. A typical CWL visit may last between a couple of days up to a week during which time the lecturer makes presentations to members of the local community, primary and secondary school students, and the local media, if possible. The goal is to maximize the benefit of the CWL to the host community.

As of September 2019, six visits have been successfully arranged:

2016: Whitehorse, YT (Christa Van Loerhoven). 2018: Ashcroft and Cache Creek, BC (Jon Willis), Nitinaht Lake, BC (Doug Johnstone), Nutashkuan, QC (Louise Edwards). 2019: The Pas, MB (Christian Marois), Igloolik, NU (Stan Metchev).

The lecturers have written very positive accounts of their experiences. Plans are currently underway in the call for applications of the 2020 CWL visits. This is arguably the first up-and-running CASCA EPO National Pillar.

It should be emphasized that *CASCA's EPO committee has always consisted of a group volunteers*, and as such the quality of the Pillar projects will only be as good as volunteer time and energy allow. To reach the goal of maximum effectiveness and impact these Pillars will require a CASCA EPO Coordinator and the funds to hire said person (and ideally a coordinator for each Pillar and the funds to hire these people). The National Pillar Projects need dedicated, clearly defined, long-term funding to develop content and market the results to Canadians.

4. Proposed 'Pillar' Funding – Past LRP recommendations, issues, and proposed solutions

We start this discussion with a look at the most recent LRP and mid-term review reports (see https://casca.ca/?page_id=4562 and <https://www.casca.ca/lrp2010/Docs/LRPReports/WhitePaperList.html>). The idea of creating a national website to promote Canadian Astronomy (which in this white paper is referred to as the e-CASCA key-stone website) dates to the LRP2000, which stated: *The LRPP strongly recommends that the Canadian Astronomical Society (CASCA) and the NRC with the participation of the CSA, create a first rank national web site for astronomy. This should be one of the highest priorities among the outreach initiatives.*

The initiative reappears in LRP 2010: *The LRPP recommends that the "AstronomyCanada.ca" website be co-developed with a brand awareness campaign led by the professional community.* Once again, however, despite being identified as a high priority by former Long Range Planners, we are revisiting the idea of a key-stone CASCA website with LRP2020.

In terms of EPO funding in general, the 2000 LRPP committee; *strongly recommended that approximately 1.5% of any project budget be allocated towards the support of related outreach efforts*. A decade later, in the LRP2010 report, we see this statement; *In support of all these issues, the LRPP thus recommends that funding agencies apportion 1.5% of funds for new facilities to public outreach*.

This “1.5% proposal” has gotten excellent endorsement by past Long Range Planners, but it has not yet been put into action by the CASCA Board. We have contemplated this and believe these are the primary reasons why:

First; what projects have been on past EPO committee lists that require funds to execute? Each iteration of CASCA’s EPO committee over the last 20 years has had their own exciting EPO objectives, undoubtedly built around managing and connecting a myriad of EPO players and entities (for example, the 2010 whitepaper on EPO by Crabtree et al. stated in its recommendations, “*Our community needs to identify a mechanism by which core EPO in Canada can be funded sustainably.*”).

The intervening CASCA Boards were subsequently faced the complicated task of taking these lofty visions and turning them into affordable and sustainable schemes with legacy. But with too many moving parts, and despite much effort, sorting out all the required details has never been accomplished.

Second; research facilities such as Gemini and CFHT, research institutes such as those at the Dunlap Institute and the Centre for Planetary Sciences at the University of Toronto, the Centre for Planetary Science and Space Exploration at Western University, the McDonald Institute for astroparticle physics at Queen’s University, the McGill Space Institute and the Institute for Research on Exoplanets in Montreal, and university entities such as the Science Outreach Centre at SMU and the Rothney Astrophysical Observatory, already do (or have started to) allocate some portion of their annual budgets to self-promotion and EPO. Consequently, these Facilities and Institutes are unlikely to buy into the idea of additionally contributing a portion of their budgets to CASCA’s EPO efforts without a clear benefit to their programs.

Third, while it is clear that the Canadian Astronomical Society supports EPO and thus recognizes the importance of EPO funding, this has not been the case for the two largest government funders of astronomy in Canada; NSERC and CFI. There is no requirement for NSERC-funded projects to have an outreach plan, and CFI funds cannot be spent on non-infrastructure items like outreach.

An example is the \$16M CHIME telescope. A collaboration led by a group of Canadian Institutions that is primarily funded by a CFI grant. In the LRP 2010, the project was praised for its *strongly focused scientific objectives*. In contrast, the project has never had a formal EPO or communications strategy. The scientists in the collaboration, responding to the incentives that they were given, spent their time planning to do the best science they could with the funding that they had. Since no funding agency required an EPO plan at the time the telescope was designed or under construction, this was simply never a priority. The lack of a collaboration-wide strategy does not imply a lack of interest in or good will towards outreach activities among its members. However, CHIME’s primary focus is getting science results and publishing those results in high-impact journals. Thus, the scattershot EPO work done by CHIME collaboration members, like most of EPO in Canada, is done by volunteers in their spare time, with no dedicated funding. This means that most taxpayers in Canada have little knowledge of CHIME, even though it is doing amazing science.

The only federal funds for EPO come via the NSERC PromoScience program. PromoScience grants will only fund 30% of a project and do not support new or pilot programs without strong prior evidence for the impact of the program. They also only fund outreach aimed at K-12 students and their teachers, leaving out all programs aimed at pre-school aged children, general postsecondary students, adults or the general public.

So, unless collaborations make the decision to spend part of their unrestricted funds as a good will gesture, no new facilities projects will dedicate part of their grant money to EPO. There is no mechanism to enforce the 1.5% proposal from the previous LRP committees.

Moving forward requires some sort of remedy to these three problems. We offer these observations:

The principle financial achievement of this National Pillar Project model is to remove barriers related to the first issue. Unlike Crabtree et al., we are not looking to manage core EPO in Canada. Instead, we wish to define a reasonable number of projects that CASCA's EPO committee can manage with the support of the CASCA Board, which have a national scope, and which give clear guidance to funds should funding be found.

With regard to the second issue, while it is good that EPO is becoming ingrained into the mandates of Canada's astronomical institutions, there is undoubtedly a good deal of overlap and redundancy. Perhaps a more streamlined approach could be found that would make possible shared EPO funding amongst institutions, increasing the likelihood that some surplus of that funding makes its way to national EPO efforts, overseen by CASCA. Smaller institutions and projects that do not have the resources to establish their own outreach programs could contribute to the CASCA outreach fund and receive in return materials and assistance.

The third issue is fundamental and can only be improved at the Government of Canada level by lobbying carried out by the CASCA Board (and perhaps other Canadian Science education organizations). But if this barrier were removed the following example shows the incredible gain in funding for CASCA EPO and astronomy education and outreach in Canada in general:

According to LRP2010 documents, \$590M was slated for Ground and Space based projects and for new Infrastructure, for the (then) upcoming 10 years (see Appendix 3 - it is likely that the LRP2020 budgetary outlook will be similar). 1.5% of this amount is ~\$9M over 10 years, or ~\$900k per year. Even 1% equates to ~600k per year which is more than sufficient to make the four National Pillars of CASCA EPO successful, relevant, and a legacy for the future.

MUCH more could be added and elaborated on here, but alas, there is only so much paper available here. As a placeholder for future discussion and writing we offer this short list;

- A budget for the optimal and effective operation of each National Pillar (including coordinator(s), website builder(s), social media manager(s), educational material designer(s), etc.)
- The optimal CASCA EPO committee and subcommittee structure to facilitate Pillar funding through CASCA Treasurer and CASCA Board approvals (note that the CWL Pillar is already funded by the Westar Trust Fund so would only require additional funds if its \$10k/yr quota were exceeded).
- An evaluative process to gauge the effectiveness of each Pillar Project, at appropriate time intervals.
- Explore soliciting funds from private donors with the aid of a professional fundraiser.
- Soliciting Pillar fund donations from CASCA members.

For more discussion on other aspects of EPO funding, please refer to the LRP2020 white paper submission E051 by Ouellette et al., especially sections 2.2 and 4.5.

5. Toward a Grand National Strategy for Canadian astronomy EPO

Like all the CASCA EPO committees that have come before, this committee also pines for day that all the various types of astronomy EPO in Canada will be strategically and efficiently managed and funded by one EPO coordinating body. How this body would look, where EPO funding would come from, and the most efficient path we can put ourselves on to reach this goal, is a matter of intense debate.

The IAU has been very active in EPO in the last decade. It now supports the Office for Astronomy Outreach and the Office of Astronomy for Development, which helps fund projects around the world, including many that would be considered EPO. Furthermore, the creation and location of the IAU Office for Astronomy Education in Canada will be announced very shortly. These international initiatives show that EPO is regarded as a key part of the astronomical community and should be supported and *funded* by the scientific community.

Many countries already have a national coordination in terms of outreach. Some examples include the Netherlands through their NOVA program and Australia with their position of Astronomer-At-Large, whose role is to support astronomy advocacy, outreach and STEM-focused education activities. Is it not time for Canada to create a similar position to oversee national EPO initiatives?

Minutia aside, we believe that the path to the building such a national astronomy EPO engine, that is a model for other countries, will be built on the lasting success of these four national CASCA EPO Pillars. If CASCA can fully support its EPO committees now and into the future, and we can demonstrate to Canada's Science Education entities that meaningful national-scale EPO projects with legacy can be built, this will lead to incredible EPO partnerships that we can't today imagine.

Appendix 1 - Results from the anonymous EPO opinion poll of CASCA members conducted at the CASCA AGM, McGill University, Montreal June 20, 2019

These 2 questions were asked during the EPO Committee's presentation at the morning LRP session. An electronic polling tool was used (TopHat), and all responses were completely anonymous.

(1) Over a typical calendar year, the number of times I actively engage in teaching/inspiring the general public;

- a) (0) b) (1-2) c) (3-4) d) (5+)

RESPONSES (total = 110):

- A) 11 (10%) B) 21 (20%) C) 35 (32%) D) 43 (39%)

(2) Your Society does many things for its members (I showed everyone this page from the CASCA website for a few minutes: https://casca.ca/?page_id=31).

Relative to all the things on that list, in your view, where does CASCA's EPO effort rank in importance;

- a) Near the top b) Pretty high c) In the middle d) Pretty low e) Near the bottom

RESPONSES (total = 119):

- A) 7 (6%) 35 (29%) 57 (48%) 19 (16%) 1 (1%)

Appendix 2 – A year-in-the-life of EPO in Canada as delivered by CASCA members and their collaborators

Results for the 2018 year are shown below. The EPO reporting form allows CASCA members to report an entire year’s worth of outreach data, and entire month, or just one individual event. There was a total of 72 data submissions pertaining to 2018, 38 of the full year variety and 34 of the individual event variety. Only 4 submissions were of the monthly variety. https://wcm.ucalgary.ca/rao/outreach_reporting_form

In total, over 71,000 members of the general public experienced some form of engaging astronomical learning due to the hard work of ~550 CASCA members and their helpers. For the sake of minimizing the use of space, only the totals are shown here (see the CASCA EPO Committee’s overview paper for more details).

Event totals reported by YEAR:	Number Engaged = 66,478	Number of Volunteers = 448
Event totals reported by MONTH:	Number Engaged = 2,436	Number of Volunteers = 13
Event totals reported by EVENT:	Number Engaged = 2,520	Number of Volunteers = 89

Appendix 3 – LRP2010 Proposed spending for the upcoming 10 years

Category		Priority	Project	\$
GROUND	Very Large (above \$100M)	1	VLOT	\$305M
	Large	1	SKA	\$60M
	Medium (\$5M-30M)	1	CHIME	\$15M
		2	CFHT new instrumentation	\$5M
		3	CCAT	\$15M
	Small (below \$5M)	1	Arctic	\$4M
		2	ngCFHT	\$2M
Subtotal				\$406M
SPACE	Large		Euclid/WFIRST/CST	\$100M
	Medium	1	IXO	\$15M
		2	SPICA	\$10M
	Small		Astro-H	\$5M
			Balloon	\$5M
			Microsatellite	\$5M
Subtotal				\$140M
Infrastructure, People			PDF's	\$11.3M
			Labs	\$32.5M
TOTAL				\$590M